

21GRD07 PlasticTrace

Deliverable 5

Summary report on the developed sample preparation methods for the measurement of SMPs ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$) and NPs ($< 0.1 \mu\text{m}$) in complex food matrices: drinking water and milk. The methods will include (i) enrichment prior to analysis, (ii) selective removal of natural background organic/inorganic matter, (iii) size fractionation/isolation, and (iv) homogenisation and partition steps. The accuracy and efficiency of the developed methods will be optimised to demonstrate a negligible effect on the particle characteristics and polymer compositions of samples

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1 Executive Summary

This document summarises the development of measurement methods for characterisation of number and mass concentration, size and size distribution as well as chemical identification of nano- and sub-micro-meter plastics in bottled water and milk matrix. This included systematic evaluation of sample preparation strategies including strategies for spiking, enrichment, matrix reduction and fractionation, as well as spike stability in the matrix. Remaining gaps and challenges associated with the detection and characterisation of nano and sub-micro plastics in complex real-world food samples are also discussed here.

2 Introduction

Plastics released into the environment continuously fragment into smaller particles due to weathering, biofouling, UV radiation as well as mechanical stress[1]. Scientific studies indicate that plastic particles with sizes below 10 μm dominate the size distribution patterns in environmental compartments, including marine and fresh waters and in food, including drinking water and milk[2-4].

At the same time, particles with such small sizes represent the most challenging fractions to be analysed due to the lack of validated measurement methods and strategies for analyte enrichment and isolation, matrix removal as well as reliable detection, identification and multiparameter characterisation, including mass, number concentration, size and size distribution[5, 6].

3 Materials

3.1 Model plastics

Polypropylene (PP) was chosen as a model polymer type, because they are commonly used in packaging and hence in direct contact with food. Nanosized fractions were produced by BAM, as part of WP1 (see D2 for details) by milling with an Ultra Turrax and subsequent sieving to achieve particles with environmental relevant properties such as irregular shapes, broad particle size distributions and different aging states mimicking particles in nature. The nanoPP material (with approximate size < 200 nm and approximate concentration < 20 $\mu\text{g/g}$, please see Deliverable D2 for details) was provided as water suspension without any stabiliser, in ~ 2 ml vials. Homogeneity of the material was assessed using PTA, whilst stability was assessed using DLS, as described in D2.

PP particles with target sizes ~ 1 - 10 μm were prepared by SINTEF using similar protocol as part of WP1 and provided as water suspensions with 0.025 wt% BSA as stabiliser. However, production yields of the target 1-10 μm PP particles were low quantity (ca. 20 mg from 500 g) and preliminary characterisation with DLS suggesting main size distribution of the isolated fraction was actually in the nanoscale (~ 250 nm), rather than the target 1-10 μm . Work is ongoing to try and isolate the 1-10 μm PP particles from another fraction (10-45 μm), where DLS revealed they were actually present. As a result, the nominal 1-10 μm fraction of the PP material was unsuitable for the purpose of the experiments described here. Therefore, all work reported here was performed using nanoPP material as the model sample.

3.2 Model matrices

Two matrices of increasing complexity were chosen for the experiments reported here:

- EVIAN bottled water (1,5 L PET Bottle, Nestle), representing simple food matrix, i.e. drinking water, and
- Baby milk powder (HIPPI 1 Bio), representing highly complex (buy liquid) food matrix

4 Methods

4.1 Matrices spiking with model samples

NanoPP material (see D2 for more details on the characteristics) was diluted ~5-100x in Evian model matrix and mixed well before analysis. Due to low level of interference (i.e. dissolved ions only) coming from the matrix components with the techniques employed in characterisation (described in the next section), the mixture was analysed without extraction or matrix reduction.

Before spiking of nanoPP into model milk matrix, the matrix itself was prepared according to the instructions given by the manufacturer. Briefly, ~1 g was dissolved in 10 ml of water (ultrapure in this case) and mixed well before use. NanoPP was then diluted ~10-100x in that matrix and mixed well. The sample was then subjected to extraction and/or fractionation prior to detection and characterisation of the plastic.

4.2 Techniques used for detection and characterisation

4.2.1 Particle tracking analysis (PTA)

PTA is a method where particles undergoing Brownian motion in a liquid suspension are illuminated by a laser and the change in position of *individual* particles over time is used to determine the number-weighted particle size and size distribution. Particle concentration is derived from the number of particles detected in the analysed sensing volume (i.e. field of view x depth). The minimal size detection limit depends on the optical properties of the sample material, typically above 10 nm for high density materials, such as gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) and above 40 nm to 50 nm for low density materials, such as biological particles or plastics. The upper size limit is roughly 1000 nm.

4.2.2 Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

DLS probes the particle motion optically in a suspension. The suspended particles are illuminated with a coherent monochromatic light source. The light scattered from the moving suspended particles (detected at Backscatter, > 173 degrees angle), has a time-dependent phase imparted to it from the time-dependent position. The optical signal received from the particles are analysed and related to scattering efficiency and intensity-weighted particle size (and size distribution). The modelling is based on Stoke-Einstein theory of Brownian motion of smooth spheres and is influenced by the viscosity and temperature. A multi-angle dynamic light scattering (MADLS) is an extension of DLS that detects light scattered at a plurality of angles relative to the incident laser beam, typically at three detection angles – e.g. backscatter (> 173 degrees), side scatter (90 degrees) and forward scatter (< 20 degrees). The temporal behaviour of the light scattered into each angle is analysed independently to produce an auto-correlation function that is unique to each angle. In MADLS, the plurality of auto-correlation functions and the time-averaged scattered intensity

are collectively analysed to derive the 'absolute' particle size distribution and particle size. Electrophoretic Light Scattering (ELS or z-DLS) measures the electrophoretic mobility of particles in dispersion. The mobility of the particle can be converted to zeta potential when dielectric constant and viscosity of the dispersion medium and Henry's function ($F(Ka)$) are known. Henry's function is the ratio of the particle radius to the electrical double-layer thickness and is often approximated to 1.0 for a non-polar system (Hückel approximation) or to 1.5 for polar systems (*Smoluchowski* approximation). In practical terms, a dispersion is introduced into a cell containing two electrodes. An electrical field is applied to the electrodes, and particles or molecules that have a net charge, or more strictly a net zeta potential, will migrate towards the oppositely charged electrode with a velocity, proportional to their charge. The particle mobility and direction (hence the electrical sign) are determined using Phase Analysis Light Scattering (PALS). PALS analyses the phase difference resulting from the frequency (Doppler) shift of light scattered from the sample compared to a mutually coherent modulated reference beam that bypasses the sample. Combining these two beams produces a modulated signal with a much smaller frequency than the light source due to constructive and destructive interference. This "beat" frequency is equal to the frequency difference between the scattered and reference beams and is used to determine the mobility of the particles.

4.2.3 Field-flow fractionation (FFF)

FFF is a separation technique without a stationary phase. The separation is achieved within a narrow, ribbon-like channel, wherein a laminar lateral flow is applied that results in a parabolic flow profile. Perpendicular to the channel flow a separation force is applied. The separation force can be realised by a second flow field (Asymmetrical Flow FFF 'AF4') or a centrifugal force (CF3) or a thermal gradient (TF3)[7]. In AF4, the separation force interacts with the Brownian motion (Diffusion) of the sample constituents, as a result smaller particles, which have a higher diffusion coefficient, will be located closer to the centre and therefore will experience a higher lateral flow due to the parabolic flow profile. To allow the flow-field (cross flow) to leave the channel bottom (accumulation wall) the accumulation wall consists of an ultrafiltration membrane with a defined cut-off.

4.2.4 SEM

SEM images have been performed at LNE with a Zeiss ULTRA-Plus equipped of a Field Emission Gun (FEG) microscope and in-Lens SE detector. All images have been carried out through secondary electrons collected by In Lens detector. The beam voltage was 3 kV and the working distance 3 mm.

4.2.5 pyGC-MS

PyGC-MS is a mass-based quantification technique. When applied to the quantification of polymers it can be a useful alternative to number-based techniques, especially as it allows both polymer identification and quantification[8-10]. The technique is based upon pyrolyzing the sample at high temperature under an oxygen free atmosphere. The pyrolysis process

thermally degrades the polymer material into smaller stable fragments or components that are subsequently transferred into the gas chromatograph (GC) where they are separated according to molecular weight. Finally, the separated fragments/components are transferred to the mass spectrometer (MS) where they are analysed. The resulting pyrogram contains peaks that correspond to the different pyrolysis products, with a mass spectrum associated with each component. For a specific type of polymer, such analysis produces a unique fingerprint that can then be used to determine the presence of that specific polymer in a sample[8]. Polymer quantification is typically conducted by constructing calibration curves from the same polymer that is the target of quantification. The technique does have some limitations, including the small sample size that can be analysed[11]. One of these concerns the fact that slightly different formulations exist for most of the polymers, meaning that the 'unique' fingerprint will vary, either in the number and type of degradation products (fragments) or the respective ratios of the different products. Another issue concerns analysis of polymer in complex samples, such as environmental or biological samples. The presence of biogenic compounds in these samples can also generate some of the same pyrolysis products (fragments) as certain polymer types. This can lead to over- and underestimation of polymer content in such samples[9].

4.3 Strategies for analyte pre-concentration and enrichment

Since most of the techniques suitable for characterisation of nano and sub-micro plastics (described above) have limitations in terms of LODs and LOQs ($>10^4 - 10^{10}$ NP g^{-1}) whilst the expected concentrations of plastics in 'real-life' drinking water and food samples is likely below these limits, analyte pre-concentration is necessary to ensure reliable detection and characterisation.

The applicability of the following preconcentration/enrichment strategies have been considered:

4.3.1 Ultrafiltration

During Ultrafiltration the liquid sample is forced through a membrane (aided by ultracentrifugation) with a specific molecular weight cut off (i.e. pore size), which retains the particles in a small volume of the liquid, while the majority of liquid matrix along with low molecular components pass through the filter and hence are removed from the sample. This allows to eliminate interfering matrix components such as salts, while the targeted particles are retained and enriched.

Advantages: salt elimination preconcentration factor 10 to 40

Drawbacks: particle loss on membrane, contamination issues, particle recovery for subsequent analysis

4.3.2 Freeze drying

During freeze drying a defined volume of the liquid sample is deep frozen and placed in a vacuum chamber, which allows the sublimation of the water from the sample, which results in the preconcentration of all constituents present in the sample.

Advantages: high preconcentration factor up to 1000

Drawbacks: enrichment of the salt mass fraction of the sample, time consuming

4.3.3 Filtration

During filtration the liquid sample is forced through a membrane with a specific pore size with the aid of vacuum, which retains the particles on the filter, while the liquid matrix and low size component pass through the filter and hence are removed from the sample. This allows to eliminate interfering matrix components such as salts, while the targeted particles are retained on the filter. Particles can be then analysed directly on the filter with microscopy or RAMAN-based techniques or can be recovered into a small volume of the liquid via leaching and sonication.

Advantages: high volumes can be processed resulting in pre-concentration factors up to 200, salt elimination

Drawbacks: particle loss on the filter, contamination issues, particle recovery for subsequent analysis

4.3.4 Cloud Point Extraction (CPE)

CPE has been recently proposed in the literature[12-15] for pre-concentrating trace amounts of nanoplastics in environmental waters. Enrichment factor of 500 have been achieved for polymers such as PS and PMMA, while no changes in size and morphology have been observed, which is essential to avoid biased results.

This approach is particularly interesting for pre-concentration prior to pyGC-MS analyses or as part of hyphenated methods combining e.g. the separation power of AF4 with the identification and mass concentration measurement of pyGC-MS

Advantages: handling of small sample volumes, high preconcentration factors up to 500

Drawbacks: particle loss, introduction of additional matrix (e.g. Triton X-45)

5. Results

5.1 Characterisation of nano and sub-micro-plastics in drinking water

Model nanoplastic material (nanoPP) spiked into drinking water matrix (Evian) was characterised for:

- Size and size distribution with: PTA, DLS, MADLS, SEM and AF4/MALS (5.1.1)
- Particle number concentration with: PTA (5.1.2)
- Mass concentration with: pyGC-MS (5.1.3)
- Zeta-potential (net charge) with: z-DLS (5.1.4)

5.1.1. Particle size and size distribution analysis

5.1.1.1. PTA Results

LGC Results:

Sample preparation: Model nano plastic material (nano PP) was diluted 100 times gravimetrically either with ultrapure water or EVIAN drinking water matrix. All aliquots were freshly prepared and measured at t=0 h and after t=24 h incubation at room temperature. Three preparations of each sample were measured 5 times under repeatability conditions.

Experimental conditions: NanoSight NS300 (Malvern Panalytical Ltd., Malvern, UK) equipped with a laser module with a wavelength at 405 nm and a high sensitivity scientific complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (sCMOS) camera and NTA software version 3.4.003 was used. Measurements were performed in flow mode, using a syringe pump connected to the Low-Volume-Flow-Cell (LVFC), operating at a pump speed of 40. Measurements were conducted at room temperature, using camera level of 11 and detection threshold of 5.

Results:

Obtained results are summarised in the table and figure below.

Table 1 Modal and mean particle diameter values obtained with PTA.

Vial ID	Diluent/ timepoint	Diameter (nm)					
		Mode n=15	StDev (n=15)	RSD (%)	Mean (n=15)	StDev (n=15)	RSD (%)
578	Elga water/t=0	111.5	12.7	11.4	149.3	4.7	3.2
578	Elga water/24hrs	121.3	15.8	13.1	147.7	5.1	3.5
578	Evian water/t=0	120.7	21.1	17.5	143.0	4.4	3.1
578	Evian water /24h	129.1	29.5	22.9	175.4	47.9	27.3

Figure 1 Particle size distribution graphs obtained using PTA.

Inherited polydispersity in all samples was observed, with modal particle sizes smaller than mean indicating non-Gaussian size distribution. Measured sizes of nanoPP in Elga water (even after 24 h incubation) are in-line with the expected values, as described in D2. However, the nanoPP material incubated in Evian water for 24 h showed an increase in mean diameter, most likely due to agglomeration/aggregation. Higher RSDs were observed, most likely due to increased variability induced by random agglomeration/aggregation of the particles.

UNITO Results:

Sample preparation:

Model nano plastic material (nano PP) was diluted 600 times gravimetrically either with ultrapure water or EVIAN drinking water matrix. All aliquots were freshly prepared and measured following up to 3 days incubation at room temperature. Three independent experiments were performed (each one in triplicate).

Experimental conditions:

PTA was performed using a ZetaView® PMX-120 (Particle Metrix GmbH, Germany) instrument, equipped with a light source wavelength of 488 nm and a 90° laser scattering video microscope with 10× magnification. After the optimisation of the instrumental parameters, the sensitivity and the shutter were set at 80 and 100, respectively and the frame rate at 30 fps; 3 × 33 videos of 1 second for each sample were recorded analysing a total of minimum ~1000 NPs per measurement.

Results:

Over time in Evian drinking water matrix an increase in average particle size ($11 \pm 2\%$) has been observed.

Figure 2 Characterisation of nanoPP in Evian with PTA.

5.1.1.2 DLS/MADLS Results

LGC Results:

Sample preparation: nano-PP MODEL sample (ID: 578) was measured neat and following 10 times dilution in either Elga or EVIAN drinking water at $t=0$ h and after $t=24$ h of incubation time at room temperature. Three independent preparations of each sample were measured 3-5 times under the repeatability conditions.

Experimental conditions: Measurements with MADLS were performed with Zetasizer Ultra (Malvern Panalytical), at angles of 173°, 90° and 13° using low-volume high-performance black Quartz Cuvette (ZEN 2112).

Results: Obtained results are summarised in Table 2 and Figure 3 below

Table 2 Average particle size obtained with MADLS

Smample	Diluent /time point	MADLS Peak 1 by Intensity (nm)	StDev (nm)	RSD (%)	MADLS Peak 2 by Intensity (nm)	StDev (nm)	RSD (%)	MADLS Peak 3 by Intensity (nm)	StDev (nm)	RSD (%)
nanoPPs 766 ID578	neat	186.0	3.4	1.8	N/A			N/A		
	Elga/t=0	186.8	3.3	1.8						
	Elga/t=24h	184.5	5.5	3.0						
	Evian/t=0	180.1	3.5	2.0						
	Evian/t=2h	404.2	6.5	1.6	173.5	11.1	6.4	3824	282.8	7.4
	Evian/t=24h	409.7	7.3	1.8	206.7	32.3	15.6	696.3	6.4	0.9

Example of MADLS size distribution graph

Figure 3 Representative MADLS particle size distribution graphs

NanoPP material showed broad (i.e. polydispersed), but monomodal size distribution in Elga water, even up to 24 h incubation. However, following >2 h incubation of nanoPP in Evian water, increase in particle size was observed compared to nanoPP in ultrapure water and nanoPP in Evian at t=0h. In addition, multiple peaks at sizes above 300 nm were also observed for such samples. This is most likely associated with particle aggregation/agglomeration in the drinking water matrix over time. Overall, mean particle size measured with MADLS was larger than mean particle size measured with PTA (see previous paragraph). This can be explained by MADLS being an intensity weighted technique and

hence influenced by the presence of larger particles, whilst PTA being a number-based technique hence more sensitive to smaller sizes. For highly polydisperse samples, like the nanoPP and with a distribution tailing towards the larger sizes (as can be seen on PTA size distribution graphs, see the previous section), such discrepancy between the number-based and intensity-based techniques is not uncommon.

INRIM Results:

Sample preparation:

Nano PP material was mixed with the media listed in the Table 3 below at half of the nominal concentration. The media tested were 0.025% of NovaChem both in MilliQ (previously filtered at 0.1 μm) and Evian, MilliQ (filtered at 0.1 μm) and Evian. The samples were measured by MADLS after 0, 1, 2 and 24 h of incubation at room temperature.

Table 3 Overview of water matrix and surfactant mixtures

Tested matrix	NanoPP : Matrix ratio
0.025% NC / MilliQ (0.1)	1:1
0.025% NC / Evian	1:1
MilliQ (0.1)	1:1
Evian	1:1

Experimental conditions:

Measurements with MADLS were performed on 1 mL of samples with Zetasizer Ultra (Malvern Panalytical, UK), at angles of 173° (back scattering angle), 90° (side scattering angle) and 13° (forward scattering angle). 5 runs per measurement were conducted on each sample. The operating temperature was maintained at 25 °C.

Results:

Figure 4 Average size of nanoPP measured with MADLS

The results showed that the influence of the drinking water matrix is visible after 24 h of incubation. The presence of surfactants such as Novachem does not prevent the agglomeration/aggregation of particles in the drinking water matrix.

5.1.1.3 High-resolution microscopy (SEM) Results

LNE Results

Sample Preparation: Sample preparation for SEM analysis is illustrated in the figure below. The final working suspension (no 2) was deposited on a TEM grid by drop casting of 2 to 6 µL suspension and dried in a desiccator. TEM grids were ozonated before use.

Figure 5 Sample preparation scheme for nanoPP analysis in drinking water using SEM

Experimental conditions:

SEM images have been performed at LNE with a Zeiss ULTRA-Plus equipped of a Field Emission Gun (FEG) microscope and in-Lens SE detector. All images have been carried out through secondary electrons collected by the in Lens detector.

The particles were on a TEM grid by drop casting of 7.5 μL suspension. The drop should form a dome on the surface of the substrate and dried over time in ambient air in a pastry box. The beam voltage was 3 kV and the working distance 3 mm.

Results:

Sample with 2 different dilution factors (x10 and x100) of the initial nano-PP suspension were analysed.

Figure 6 Characterisation of nanoPP with SEM

As shown in figure 6 a significant agglomeration state was observed compared to samples which contain just the initial nanoPP suspension and similarly to what was observed directly in suspension with light scattering based methods. This could be caused by the high dissolved concentration of Ca and Mg in the drinking water matrix.

5.1.1.4 AF4-MALS

POSTNOVA Results

Sample preparation:

Model nanoPP sample was diluted in Evian drinking water and ultrapure (UPW) water. Samples were transferred to an autosampler vial and measured in triplicate using a fractionation and a direct injection method. Both, the fractionation and the direct injection method were performed using 0.01% SDS as an eluent. Additionally, blank measurements were performed by replacing the sample by eluent and applying the same method as for the sample measurements. In total 4 different concentrations, which correspond to a 30x, 20x, 10x, 5x dilution of nano-PP in the Evian drinking water matrix were prepared. In a second experiment the time dependence for potential agglomeration/aggregation was investigated. Therefore, the native nanoPP was diluted 5x in EVIAN drinking water and analysed directly after preparation and after 1 h, 2 h, 4 h and 24 h. Each time point was prepared as an individual aliquot.

Experimental conditions:

AF4 measurements were performed using the AF4 system from Postnova Analytics (AF2000 Multi Flow FFF) including an autosampler, and a channel thermostat, which was equipped with an analytical fractionation channel with a tip-to-tip length of 277 mm, a shoulder width of 20 mm and a hip width of 5 mm. A regenerated cellulose (RC) membrane of 10 kDa molecular weight cut-off and a Mylar spacer of 350 µm height were placed in the fractionation channel. The AF4 system was connected to a UV detector, MALS (Multi-Angle Light Scattering) detector.

For instrument control the AF2000 software version 2.2.0.1 and for data evaluation the NovaAnalysis version 2408 (Postnova Analytics) were applied. System performance must be checked after hardware changes of the system and at regular intervals for quality control purposes according to ISO/TS 21362:2018¹ and manufacturer recommendations.

An initial cross flow rate of 1.20 mL/min and an injection flow of 0.20 mL/min was used. The detector flow rate was 0.50 mL/min. The injection and focusing time were set to 6 min, the transition time to 0.2 min. After the focusing phase the cross-flow rate was first kept constant for 0.2 min and then followed a power decay for 40 min to 0.10 mL/min. This final cross flow step was kept constant for another 20 min. Afterwards a rinse step of 10 min minimised potential carry over effects and ensured reproducible conditions for subsequent measurements. A typical injection volume of 20 µL was used for the characterisation measurements.

Results:

As shown in figures below the AF4-MALS analysis indicated a significant agglomeration of the nano PP material depending on the dilution factor of the drinking water matrix (Evian) compared to the results observed for the analysed pure nanoPP (in Elga). This is, in particular, indicated by the increased retention times of the peaks in the fractogram, as well as by the increased R_g calculated based on the MALS data (see table below). Also a distinct shoulder has been observed indicating different agglomeration states as has been observed also during the MADLS analysis. The results showed increasing size distribution and increased agglomeration for decreasing dilution factors. Nevertheless, also a dilution factor of 30 times yielded in a significant increase for the size distribution. The peak maximum of all EVIAN drinking water samples increased compared to the native nanoPP sample. The $R_{g,50}$ value increased from the native nanoPP sample to the 30x sample from 73.0 nm to 79.0 nm. And further increased from 30x dilution to 5x dilution to 93.0 nm.

In another experiment the agglomeration tendency as a function of time was evaluated. After defined time points the samples were injected, fractionated and subsequently characterised by the MALS detector. Only slight agglomeration was observed directly after mixing, but after 2 hours of incubation at room temperature the agglomeration was significant. The fractogram showed a decreasing peak height as well as an additional peak at around 50 min.

Figure 7 Characterisation of nanoPP with AF4-MALS

Figure 8 Characterisation of nanoPP with AF4-MALS

Representative AF4-MALS fractograms of nanoPP in Evian drinking water matrix. Figure 7) The final fractograms with the absolute scattering intensities of native nanoPP (red) and of nanoPP in EVIAN drinking water showed a clear shift of the maximum retention time and the full peak to larger retention times compared to the native nanoPP sample. Furthermore, a distinct shoulder was present for nanoPP in EVIAN drinking water. Figure 8) Fractograms overlaying the 90° MALS scattering signals normalised to allow a better comparison of the size distribution changes. It was observed that the size distribution and therefore the agglomeration, which is correlated with larger retention times and increased peak broadness, increased with decreasing dilution factor. The R_g distributions (dotted lines) are comparable across the main peaks. Fractogram of native nanoPP (red), 5x dilution factor (green), 10x dilution factor (light blue), 20x dilution factor (yellow) and 30x dilution factor (dark blue).

Table 4 Summary of the Rg values obtained from MALS scattering data for different dilution factors.

	Rg max mals / nm	Rg w mals / nm	Rg 10 mals / nm	Rg 50 mals / nm	Rg 90 mals / nm
NanoPP Testmaterial	73.1	72.7	46.7	73.0	95.5
NanoPP-Evian 5x	79±3	103±4	63±2	93±2	149±6
NanoPP-Evian 10x	79.7±0.4	94±1	59.4±0.2	86.6±0.6	132±2
NanoPP-Evian 20x	76±5	85±2	56±2	81±2	115±3
NanoPP-Evian 30x	78±3	82±1	51.1±0.6	79±1	114±3

Figure 9 Representative AF4-MALS fractograms of nanoPP in EVIAN drinking water matrix at different time points. The MALS scattering signal at 90° showed a decreasing intensity with increasing incubation time. After 2 h significant agglomeration was observed, which is indicated by an additional peak at around 50 min.

LNE Results

Sample preparation: Model nanoPP sample was characterised by AF4/UV/MALS without any dilution, neither sample treatment as filtration or ultrasonication. To study the effect of the mineral water matrix, model nanoPP was diluted 10 to 100 times in Evian water. Stabilisation of nanoPP was performed using SDS 0.03% right after the spiking in Evian.

Experimental conditions:

The MD-AF4 applied in this study was an AF4 system (AF2000 Postnova Analytics) coupled to multiangle laser light scattering (MALS) (DAWN HELEOS II, Wyatt Technology) equipped with 18 angles and UV (SPD-20A, Shimadzu) detectors. An analytic AF4 channel (335 mm x60 mm) metal-free (Postnova Analytics) was used. The carrier was prepared by dissolving Novachem (Postnova Analytics) in ASTM Type I ultrapure water and filtering through a 0.1 µm filter (RC, Postnova Analytics).

The channel out-let flow rate was 0.5 mL/min. Main separation parameters are reported in Figure 10. MALS data treatment was performed using the Berry model of second degree, 11 angles and the Astra Software (Wyatt Technology). For MALS data treatment and for recovery calculation the UV detector was used. The uncertainty associated to the gyration radius was established as the combination of the repeatability and of the average MALS model uncertainty. Blanks consisting in carrier were injected between samples: no carry over was observed.

Results:

The time dependence of the agglomeration/agglomeration of nanoPP in EVIAN was tested using AF4/MALS. The obtained results are summarised in the figure below.

Figure 10 LNE optimised parameters for AF4/UV/MALS: main parameters, separation field (cross-flow as a function of time), MALS and UV signal intensity.

For each sample, three replicates were analysed at day1 and three replicates at day10. The results of the characterisation are summarised in Table 5 and resulted in a very good homogeneity in size with recoveries > 70%.

Table 5 Summary of the R_g values obtained from MALS scattering data on three different vials, with their associated uncertainties ($k=1$), and recovery values.

	Rn (nm)	Uncertainty	Rw (nm)	Uncertainty	Rz (nm)	Uncertainty	Recovery
<i>ID 492</i>	83	6%	88	6%	94	7%	71%
<i>ID 719</i>	80	5%	84	5%	89	5%	75%
<i>ID 777</i>	80	4%	85	4%	90	4%	75%

To study the effect of the mineral water matrix, model nanoPP was diluted 10 to 100 times in Evian water and analysed directly after preparation and after 1 h, 6 h, and 36 h. Dilution in Evian water showed an increase of the size as a function of the dilution factor (Figure 11). On the other side, increasing residence in the Evian matrix resulted in a shift of the fractograms to higher retention values associated to an increase of the average size (data not shown), as previously displayed by the other participants using FFF approaches. After 36 h very low MALS signals were observed, probably due to agglomeration of the particles and loss inside the channel.

Figure 11 Increase of the size measured by MALS as a function of dilution in Evian water.

Partial stabilization of nanoPP was obtained using SDS 0.03% right after the spiking in Evian (Figure 12). When comparing fractograms obtained for nanoPP spiked in Evian and immediately analysed or analysed after 6h, with nanoPP stabilised with SDS, we observe similar MALS signals and the same size distribution than in pure Nano-PP.

Figure 12 Example of stabilization of Nano-PP using SDS 0.03%.

Summary of the obtained particle size and size distribution data across the techniques

All techniques used in the work reported here have detected an increase in size of the nanoPP material in Evian water compared to nanoPP in Elga. This could be explained by particle agglomeration/aggregation induced by the presence of Ca and Mg ions and other salts. However, the mean size values obtained using these different techniques vary. This can be explained by the physical principles of the methods. Intensity weighted ensemble techniques, like MADLS, are influenced by the presence of larger particles, whilst number-based methods like PTA or SEM, or size resolved ensemble methods like AF4/MALS are more sensitive to smaller sizes. For highly polydispersed samples, like the nanoPP with size distribution tailing towards the larger sizes such discrepancy between the number-based and intensity-based techniques is not uncommon. In addition to this, solution – based techniques like PTA detect particle hydrodynamic size (which includes the hydration layer), whilst solid-state techniques, like SEM measure only particle core diameter (excluding the hydration layer).

For a more detailed discussion on the method's comparability and applicability to the characterisation of pristine nanoPP, please refer to Deliverables D2 and D6.

5.1.2. Particle number concentration using PTA

LGC Results:

Sample preparation: Model nano plastic material (nano PP) was diluted 100 times gravimetrically either with ultrapure water or Evian drinking water matrix. All aliquots were freshly prepared and measured at t=0 h and after t=24 h incubation at room temperature. Three preparations of each sample were measured 5 times under repeatability conditions.

Experimental conditions: NanoSight NS300 (Malvern Panalytical Ltd., Malvern, UK) equipped with a laser module with a wavelength at 405 nm and a high sensitivity scientific complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (sCMOS) camera and NTA software version 3.4.003 was used. Measurements were performed in flow mode, using a syringe pump connected to the Low-Volume-Flow-Cell (LVFC), operating at a pump speed of 40. Measurements were conducted at room temperature, using camera level of 11 and detection threshold of 5.

Results:

Obtained results are summarised in the table and figure below.

Table 5 Particle number concentration values obtained with PTA.

Vial ID	Diluent/ timepoint	Particle number concentration (g ⁻¹)		
		Mean (n=15)	StDev (n=15)	RSD (%)
578	Elga water/t=0	2.14E+10	1.58E+09	7.4
578	Elga water/24hrs	2.17E+10	2.63E+09	12.1
578	Evian water/t=0	1.93E+10	1.83E+09	9.5
578	Evian water /24h	1.05E+10	6.77E+09	64.5

The nanoPP material incubated in Evian water for 24 h showed a significant decrease in particle number, compared to particles suspended in ultrapure water. Higher RSDs were also observed. These are most likely associated with random agglomeration/aggregation of the particles in this media and are aligned with the increase in particle size (due to agglomeration/aggregation) observed by this technique and discussed in the previous section when using PTA (Table 1).

UNITO Results:

Sample preparation:

Model nano plastic material (nano PP) was diluted 600 times gravimetrically either with ultrapure water or Evian drinking water matrix. All aliquots were freshly prepared and measured following up to 3 days incubation at room temperature. Three independent experiments were performed (each one in triplicate).

Experimental conditions:

PTA was performed using a ZetaView® PMX-120 (Particle Metrix GmbH, Germany) instrument, equipped with a light source wavelength of 488 nm and a 90° laser scattering video microscope with 10xmagnification. After the optimisation of the instrumental parameters, the sensitivity and the shutter were set at 80 and 100, respectively and the frame rate at 30 fps; 3 × 33 videos of 1 second for each sample were recorded analysing a total of minimum ~1000 NPs per measurement.

Results:

Over time in Evian drinking water matrix a significant decrease of particle concentration (at 5 h of $18 \pm 2\%$; and at 3 days of $74 \pm 2\%$) has been observed.

Figure 13 Characterisation of nanoPP in Evian with PTA.

Summary of the obtained particle number concentration results

The particle number concentration values of nanoPP material incubated in Evian water for 24 h showed a significant decrease, compared to particles suspended in ultrapure water. Higher These are most likely associated with random agglomeration/aggregation of the particles in this media and are aligned with the increase in particle size (due to agglomeration/aggregation) observed by this technique and discussed in the previous section. Good comparability between results obtained by UNITO and LGC using PTA instrument from two different manufacturers were obtained. Please refer to D6 for more detailed comparison on the techniques.

5.1.3 Mass concentration (pyGC-MS)

SINTEF Results

Sample preparation:

The sample preparation procedure consists of the following steps:

- 1 mL aliquots of the nanoPP stock suspensions were diluted to 20 mL with EVIAN water in glass vials, evaporated to dry (90 °C) overnight. Based upon quantification of the nanoPP stock suspension using pyGC-MS, this produced a nominal nanoPP concentration of 17 µg/L in the EVIAN water samples.
- Each sample (n=5) was extracted three times with non-miscible xylene solvent to dissolve and isolate the PP material from the water matrix.
- The water was then removed, and the volume of the xylene extract was adjusted to 10 mL.
- Blank samples containing only EVIAN water and no nanoPP were also included in the analysis to determine background levels of PP in the EVIAN and to account for any PP contamination from other sources during the sample processing.
- Finally, a sub-sample (50 µL) of the xylene extract from each sample was transferred to pyrolysis crucibles and solvent removed by evaporation prior to analysis by pyGC-MS.
- A calibration curve was constructed using an inhouse PP reference material and used for quantification.

Experimental conditions:

Analysis was performed using a Frontier Multi-Shot Pyrolyzer (PY-3030D) coupled to an Agilent 7890A GC with an Agilent 5975C MS (Py-GC/MS) (Santa Clara, CA, USA). The pyrolyzer was operated in single-shot mode with pyrolysis at 600 °C (1.0 min). The pyrolyzer interface and GC inlet temperatures were 320 °C, and the split ratio was 25:1. The carrier gas was helium at a constant flow of 1 mL/min. Separation was achieved using a Frontier Ultra ALLOY+-5 capillary column (30 m length, 0.25 µm film thickness, and 0.25 mm internal diameter). The column oven temperature was programmed at 40 °C (2 min) and ramped up by 20 °C/min until it reached 320 °C (25 min hold). The transfer line temperature was 320 °C, the ion source temperature was 230 °C, and the quadrupole temperature was 150 °C. The ion source was operated in SIM mode according to the tables below. Samples are run in randomised order, with triplicate calibration samples run throughout the series, also in randomised order. Analysis was carried out by pyGC-MS (600 °C) in selected ion monitoring (SIM) mode, using several established target peaks for quantification of PP:

- 2,4-Dimethylhept-1-ene using marker ions m/z 70, 126.
- 2,4,6-Trimethyl-1-nonene (meso) using marker ions m/z 69, 97.

- 2,4,6-Trimethyl-1-nonene (racemic) using marker ions m/z 69, 97
- 2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (isotactic) using marker ions m/z 69, 111.
- 2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (heterotactic) using marker ions m/z 69, 111.
- 2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (syntactic) using marker ions m/z 69, 111.

External calibration curves were prepared from an inhouse standard PP reference material by complete solvent dissolution and subsequent dilution to different concentrations.

Results:

The concentration of nanoPP in the stock suspension was determined using each of the 6 different marker peaks (Table 6). The calculated PP concentration varied from 2.7 µg/mL (using 2,4-Dimethylhept-1-ene) to 17 µg/mL (using 2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (het)), reflecting differences in the peak ratios between the nanoPP material and the in-house reference material used for establishing the calibration curves.

The average PP concentration in the nanoPP-spiked EVIAN water samples (n=6) was then determined for each sample using all 6 different marker ions. The calculated PP concentration in the spiked EVIAN water samples varied from 2±3 µg (using 2,4,6-Trimethyl-1-nonene (meso) or 2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (iso)) to 50±9 µg (using 2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (het)). The range in estimated average nanoPP concentrations also reflected the differences in the peak ratios between the nanoPP material and the in-house reference material used for establishing the calibration curves.

Next, the average PP concentration present in the blank EVIAN water samples (i.e. background levels) were determined using the same approach. The calculated PP concentration in the blank EVIAN water samples varied from 0.1±0.2 µg (using 2,4,6-Trimethyl-1-nonene (race) or 2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (syn)) to 42.3±0.2 µg (using 2,4-Dimethylhept-1-ene). Again, the range in estimated average nanoPP concentrations reflected the differences in the peak ratios between the nanoPP material and the in-house reference material used for establishing the calibration curves.

Finally, the blank subtracted nanoPP concentrations present in the spiked EVIAN water samples were determined and the percentage recovery calculated. The blank subtracted PP concentration in the nanoPP-spiked EVIAN water samples varied from 21±4 µg (using 2,4,6-Trimethyl-1-nonene (meso) or 2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (iso)) to 19±4 µg (using 2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (het)).

It is important to note that the results showed relatively high concentrations of PP in the blank EVIAN water samples compared to the nanoPP-spiked EVIAN water samples, which may originate from the EVIAN water or from the reagents, sample preparation methods and instruments used in the study. When the average PP concentration in the spiked EVIAN water samples is subtracted with the average PP concentration in the blank samples (for each respective marker peak) the final nanoPP recoveries ranged from 57% (based on 2,4-Dimethylhept-1-ene) to 114% (based on 2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (het)).

Table 6 Summary of the pyGC-MS measurements for (i) the stock nanoPP suspensions, (ii) the nanoPP-spiked EVIAN water, the blank EVIAN water, (iv) the blank subtracted nanoPP-spiked EVIAN water, and (v) the percentage recovery of PP from spiked EVIAN water samples. Concentrations and percentage recoveries are presented for each of the PP marker ions used for quantification.

Stock nanoPP suspension concentrations (1 mL spiked in each Evian water sample)						
$\mu\text{g/mL}$ stock	PP 2,4- Dimethylhept- 1-ene	PP 2,4,6- Trimethyl- 1-nonene (meso)	PP 2,4,6- Trimethyl- 1-nonene (race)	PP 2,4,6,8- Tetramethyl- 1-undecene (iso)	PP 2,4,6,8- Tetramethyl- 1-undecene (het)	PP 2,4,6,8- Tetramethyl- 1-undecene (syn)
avg (n=6)	2.7	3.5	9.5	2.8	17	3.7
sd	0.5	0.7	2.1	0.6	4	0.8
%RSD	19	20	22	23	22	22
nanoPP-spiked EVIAN water (n=6)						
$\mu\text{g/sample}$	PP 2,4- Dimethylhept- 1-ene	PP 2,4,6- Trimethyl- 1-nonene (meso)	PP 2,4,6- Trimethyl- 1-nonene (race)	PP 2,4,6,8- Tetramethyl- 1-undecene (iso)	PP 2,4,6,8- Tetramethyl- 1-undecene (het)	PP 2,4,6,8- Tetramethyl- 1-undecene (syn)
avg	44	2	7	2	50	3
sd	2	3	5	3	9	4
%RSD	5	120	74	151	18	141
Blank EVIAN water (n=3, only water)						
avg	42.3	0.3	0.1	0.2	31.1	0.1
sd	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.3	2.1	0.1
%RSD	0	89	173	173	7	173
Blank subtracted nanoPP-spiked EVIAN water (n=6)						
avg	1.55	2	7	2	19	3
sd	0.07	3	13	4	4	6
%RSD	5	150	189	230	20	223
Recovery (%) of PP from spiked EVIAN water samples						
avg	57	58	72	67	114	72
sd	11	88	136	154	35	161
%RSD	19	151	190	231	31	224

Overall, pyGC-MS provided a range of average nanoPP percentage recoveries from the spiked EVIAN water samples. Five of PP marker peaks used for PP quantification indicated less than 100% recovery (range 57-72%), while the 2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (het)

marker peak indicated a recovery of 114%. The primary issues appear to be related to the differences in marker peak ratios between the nanoPP material spiked into the EVIAN water and the in-house PP reference material used to generate the external calibration curves for quantification. It is therefore not possible to say which of the marker peaks provides the most accurate quantification, although the relatively close distribution of recovery values for 5 of the marker peaks (57-72%) relative to the value determined when quantifying by the 2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene (het) marker peak, suggest these are the most accurate. Given the various sample preparation steps, it is likely that some of the spiked PP material is lost during sample work up and so a percentage recovery below 100% is most likely.

Importantly, this work highlights a potentially critical issue with using pyrolysis GC-MS for the quantification of PP (and perhaps other polymer types), where the ratios of the marker peaks can vary between different types of PP material. For the most accurate quantification of PP in any sample, the external calibration curve must be generated using the same material present in the 'real' samples. This is potential possible in a study such as this where the type of PP in the 'real' samples was known and theoretically could have been used to generate the calibration curves. However, in any samples with an unknown polymer content, it is not possible to know which polymer type to use for quantification purposes. In the current study, the nanoPP stock suspensions were prepared by one lab and distributed to others to assess the concentration of nanoPP using their conventional methods. In the case of pyGC-MS, we see that using different types of PP materials in the real samples and for generating calibration curves can lead to variations in the amount recovered and it is not possible to say accurately how much of the 'missing' PP material results from the differences in the PP materials that were spiked into the EVIAN water and used for generating calibration curves, and how much is lost as a result of the sample preparation method.

Interestingly, the pyGC-MS approach employed in this study also highlighted that the blank EVIAN water samples also contained high amounts of PP, relative to the amount of nanoPP that was spiked in. This background PP could either be already present in the EVIAN water or introduced during the sample processing steps. As the water came from plastic bottles, it is most likely that these background levels come from packaging rather than the sample processing (i.e. contamination).

5.1.4 Zeta potential (z-DLS)

UNITO Results:

Sample preparation:

Model nano plastic material (nano PP) was diluted 10 times either with ultrapure water or EVIAN drinking water matrix. All aliquots were freshly prepared and measured after 10 minutes incubation at room temperature. Analysis was performed in triplicate.

Experimental conditions:

Z-potentials and conductivity were measured using a Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern) electrophoretic light scattering analyser and a DTS1070 Folded Capillary Zeta Cell (Malvern).

Results:

As shown in the figure 14 below in ultra-pure water the Z-potential was significantly stronger, likely due to the significant lower conductivity of the ultra-pure water compared to the Evian drinking water matrix. This indicated that electrostatic colloidal stabilisation mechanism may be responsible for the aggregation/agglomeration observed in the drinking water matrix, and supports the results described in previous section.

Figure 14 Z-potential of the nanoPP material measured with z-DLS

5.2 Pre-concentration/enrichment strategies

5.2.1 Ultrafiltration (UNITO)

Preliminary tests showed a significant loss of the material as well as other issues associated with recovery of the concentrate from the devices. In addition, the commercially available devices allow only the processing of small sample volumes, which makes it difficult to process large representative sample volumes. Due to these drawbacks no further experiments have been conducted.

5.2.2 Freeze Drying (BAM)

The initial experiments showed that sufficiently large volumes can be pre-concentrated and therefore high pre-concentration factors are possible, which is critically important for majority of analytical techniques, which will require pre-concentration by several orders of magnitude. However, freeze drying does not allow the removal of the sample matrix, which is critical when working with food, from simple bottled water (already containing significant quantity of salts) to milk. Initial experiment showed that pre-concentration by freeze-drying results in significant losses of the material. Due to these drawbacks no further experiments have been conducted related to freeze drying as a suitable preconcentration method.

5.2.3 Filtration (LNE)

To test the feasibility of using filtration for particle enrichment and initial matrix reduction a miniaturised, polymer free filtration setup has been used. Around 500 mL EVIAN water was spiked with 100 μ L of the nanoPP suspension, which corresponds to a dilution of \sim 5000x. The samples were filtered over a 100 nm filter membrane. The filters were then cut and placed in 3 mL of Novachem (NC) 0.0125% water solution. The samples were sonicated for 40 min. to recover the particles into the Novachem solution as shown in the figure 15 below. Around 150 μ L were injected into the used AF4-MALS setup, which corresponds to a 10-fold dilution of the original nanoPP suspension.

Figure 15 Recovery of nanoPP particles from the filter.

Figure below shows the AF4/MALS analysis of the 10 times diluted original nanoPP suspension (blue line) as well as the injected sample obtained from the filtration experiment (red line). The fractograms indicate a significant loss of the nanoPP upon the filtration. Because of this, no further filtration experiments were performed. This approach should be developed more, using suitable filter materials and testing different parameters to recover particles on the filter surface.

Figure 16 AF4/MALS analysis of the recovered nanoPP sample from \sim 100 nm filtration membrane

5.2.4 Cloud point extraction (LNE)

The figure below provides an overview of the CPE procedure employed here[15].

Figure 17 Schematic representation of the CPE procedure

Nano-PP sample following CPE procedure was analysed with AF4/MALS. Several parameters influencing the performance of the extraction were varied: temperature, extraction time, sample volume, type of reactor. Examples of the obtained results are summarised in Figure 18. Conditions 1) and 2) led to significant losses of the nanoPP material.

Figure 18 AF4/MALS Analysis of the nanoPP following CPE.

Condition 3) allowed recovering a population of size close to the reference nanoPP. Nevertheless, residual contamination from the extraction method eluted in the beginning of the separation (before 20 min). This could be due to incomplete degradation of Triton X-45, presence of micelles or presence of agglomerated nanoPP particle eluting in steering mode. Experiments are still ongoing, exploring two perspectives: (1) increase the furnace time and improve the resuspension; (2) replace TX-45 thermal degradation step by chemical digestion using NaClO or TMAH (different dilutions, reaction times, temperature).

5.2.5 AF4 online preconcentration using double FFF channel

Figure 19 AF4/MALS analysis of the nanoPP using double FFF channel. The fractogram shows reference nanoPP (red signal) and nanoPP separated after 500x dilution and inline preconcentration (blue signal).

AF4/MALS was tested for inline preconcentration. Inline preconcentration in the AF4 channel using large volume injection has already been employed in literature allowing quantification at concentrations 10 to 500 times lower than in standard conditions. The aim of the work here was to replace the large loop with a channel, in order to be able to preconcentrate larger volumes in reasonable time. Hence, a first channel was used for preconcentration and a second channel for focalisation and fractionation (Figure 19). This approach, although innovative, showed low recovery due to double interaction in the two channels between the membrane and the particles, and higher size distribution as compared to the initial size of the nanoPP revealing potential agglomeration during the preconcentration. Given its technical complexity and the time required, this approach has ultimately been discontinued.

5.3. Characterisation of nano and sub-micro-plastics in milk matrix

Model nano plastic material (nanoPP) spiked into milk matrix (Hipp baby formula, prepared as described in section 4) requires matrix reduction prior to analysis. The feasibility of using the following matrix removal approaches were tested:

- Direct fractionation with AF4/MALS (5.3.1)
- Chemical extraction (5.3.2)
- Enzymatic extraction (5.3.3)

5.3.1 Direct fractionation using AF4/MALS

Sample preparation:

The Hipp baby formula was prepared as described in section 4) with 4.3 g to 30 mL of ultrapure water (UPW). Prior to injection the milk was diluted 100x in UPW.

Experimental conditions:

The AF4 system was used as described in section 5.1.1.4. A 10 kDa regenerated cellulose membrane was installed in the AF4 channel, which was equipped with a 350 μm spacer height. The carrier liquid consisted of 10 mM phosphate buffer, pH=7.4. A fractionation method with an initial cross flow rate of 3.0 mL/min was applied. After a constant step of 16 min the cross-flow rate was decreased linearly to 0.5 mL/min within 20 min. After a power decay of 12 min to asymptotically reach the final cross flow rate of 0.038 mL/min, this final elution step was kept constant for 30 min. At the end a 10 min rinse step is used to remove potential memory effects and to remove large particles from the channel.

In a second experiment the carrier liquid was adjusted to 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH=7.4 + 7.5 mM SDS to modify the retention time of the milk constituents while fractionating the nanoPP sample.

Results:

Figure 20 below shows the results obtained on 100 times diluted milk sample. The presence of the complex mixture of milk constituents resulted in a broad size distribution. The large scattering signals of milk constituents and their broad size distribution showed the need for a sample preparation strategy to identify nanoPP particles.

Figure 20

Representative AF4-MALS fractograms of milk matrix showing the 90° MALS angle.

The adjustment of the carrier liquid with a higher concentration of SDS resulted in the fractogram below. The scattering signal at 90° for native nanoPP and milk with a dilution factor of 100 is overlaid. The adjusted carrier liquid did not result in a significant different retention time of milk constituents compared to native nanoPP. As a result, we can conclude that a more comprehensive sample preparation strategy is necessary to remove matrix components and to finally be able to identify nanoPP in the milk matrix.

Figure 21 AF4-MALS Analysis in SDS overlaying fractograms of milk (100x dilution, red color) and native nanoPP (dark blue) and a system blank measurement.

5.3.2 Chemical extraction

Acid digestion

Sample preparation:

Milk sample was prepared as described in section 4). After sufficient mixing the milk was sonicated in a sonication bath for 5 min. Two aliquots were prepared, one with nanoPP and one, where nanoPP was replaced by UPW. 200 μ L nanoPP stock solution or 200 μ L UPW, respectively, was spiked into milk to reach a final volume of 2 mL. After dilution the samples were manually shook and 20 mg citric acid was added, followed by 5 min sonication bath treatment and overnight roll mixing. The final sample was diluted 50 and 100 times in UPW, respectively, and filtered through a 1 μ m PES syringe filter.

Experimental conditions:

AF4 system and method parameters were described above in section 5.1.1.4.

Results:

The AF4-MALS results shown in the figure below indicate material agglomeration/aggregation. Digestion with citric acid has not improved the outcome. The described sample preparation strategy using citric acid did not yield in a matrix removal to clearly identify nanoPP particles. The resulting suspension showed a broad size distribution and caused increased noise levels on the MALS scattering signals.

Figure 22 AF4-MALS analysis of the nanoPP spiked in milk, following matrix digestion with citric acid. Fractograms showing the MALS scattering signal at 90° for native nanoPP (dark blue), nanoPP spiked into milk with a final dilution of 50 times (light blue) and 100 times (orange), respectively, and milk blank are displayed. The void peak at 6 min indicates the presence of very large components/agglomerates/aggregates.

Alkaline digestion Hereon Results

Sample preparation:

Milk sample was prepared as described in section 4). Alkaline digestion stock solution consisting of 50 g KOH, 165 g NaOCl (13%), 1 mL TWEEN 20 (10%) and 340 mL MilliQ for matrix reduction was used. Two different samples were tested: Milk Matrix spiked with Nano PS Spheres (500 nm) and Milk Matrix without further spiking. Both samples were incubated with 10 mL of the digestion stock solution at 40°C for 12 h. Digested samples were subsequently filtered over 1 µm glass fibre filters. Filtrate of the unspiked sample was measured as a blank for background and as a matrix for nanoPP (diluted 1:10).[16]

Experimental conditions:

Centrifugal FFF (cFFF) measurements were performed using the cFFF system from Postnova Analytics (CF2000) including an autosampler, a Degasser unit and a UVD disinfection unit. The system was equipped with an analytical fractionation channel with a thickness of 231 µm, a channel area of 100 cm² and a void volume of 2 mL. 0.2% NovaChem100 was used as solvent. The cFFF system was connected to a MALS detector[17].

A typical injection volume of 20 µL was used for the measurements. The used method contained of a start speed of 3500 rpm maintaining a flow rate of 1.5 mL/min. The injection time was set to 38 seconds, followed by a focusing time of 5 min.

After each run a rinse step of 10 min was conducted to overcome potential carry over effects and ensured reproducible conditions for subsequent measurements. At the end of each measuring batch a blank run was performed injecting only MilliQ.

Results:

The procedure allowed to reduce the matrix, however still agglomeration/aggregation occurred. Overall, the filtration process was performed overnight and resulted in an appropriate output only for the milk matrix, which was not spiked with PS Spheres before digestions. This indicates that the spiked PS Spheres further agglomerate with the milk matrix/ matrix residue after digestion, which leads to significant clogging of the filter. Digested milk matrix without spiking was measured using cFFF (as previously described) and resulted in sufficiently low background signal that measurement spiked with nanoPP was conducted. Results indicated that agglomeration of nanoPP in this matrix occurred, which was shown by broad and shifted elution peaks to biases in the particle size measurement ($d_n = 211 \text{ nm} \pm 4 \text{ nm} (n=2)$).

Figure 23 AF4/MALS characterisation of alkaline digests

5.3.3 Chemical extraction/Enzymes

Preliminary experiments using a mixture of protease/lipase and subsequent analysis of protein digests with AF4/MALS showed similar outcome as chemical digestion, with significant agglomeration/aggregation of nanoPP observed.

Experiments using Proteinase K (followed by fractionation is SDS) are still ongoing.

6. Outlook

6.1 Preconcentration and Enrichment SMP/NP from water matrix

Out of the tested pre-concentration strategies CPE and ultrafiltration gave the most promising results. Although significant losses of nanoPP material occurred in both cases, the use of stabilising agents, such as biomolecules (proteins or sugars), buffers and/or surfactants could be investigated in the future, as might yield better results.

6.2 Matrix reduction

It was possible to digest the milk matrix using both chemical and enzymatic digestion, it is also possible to fractionate it from the analyte. However, since the matrix itself significantly affects the characteristics of nanoPP (i.e. induces particle agglomeration/aggregation) it was not possible to draw conclusion as of which procedure yield the most promising results. In the future, different model sample could be used to further evaluate the suitability of enzymatic and chemical extraction protocols.

7 Conclusions

The results described here clearly indicate the challenges associated with characterisation of $> 10 \mu\text{m}$ plastics. Analyte enrichment prior to analysis is prerequisite for reliable detection at the native concentrations in liquid food, and so far, a protocol yielding in reasonable analyte recovery could not be identified. Matrix reduction, necessary for analysis in complex food matrices, is also very challenging, and although promising preliminary results were obtained, the suitability of the tested procedure to plastic particles could not be verified due to instability of the nanoPP model sample in the milk matrix itself (i.e. prior to digestion). The used model sample (nanoPP) showed signs of aggregation/agglomeration even in simple drinking water matrix, but despite this it was technically possible to characterise key measurands (i.e. particle size, size distribution, mass and number concentration as well as zeta-potential) in this matrix with the used techniques described in this report.

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